

Article Title:

Necropolitics and Healthcare: Analyzing the Impact of the October 2023 Gaza Conflict.

I am pleased to submit my manuscript entitled “**Necropolitics and Healthcare: Analyzing the Impact of the October 2023 Gaza Conflict**”. This article explores the recent escalation of violence in Gaza, specifically focusing on its profound effects on the healthcare system and the broader implications of the conflict through a necropolitical lens.

In this article, I provide a comprehensive examination of the October 2023 war on Gaza, beginning with a historical overview of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict to offer context for the Gaza Strip’s unique situation. I then analyze how the conflict, which commenced on October 7, 2023, has notably targeted the healthcare system, causing significant humanitarian concerns. Finally, the article utilizes necropolitical theory to interpret the nature and consequences of the conflict, providing a critical framework for understanding the political and social dimensions of the violence.

The significance of this study lies in its timely and critical analysis of a conflict that has had a devastating impact on civilian infrastructure, particularly healthcare. The combination of historical context and theoretical analysis aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the ongoing situation and its broader implications for conflict studies and humanitarian response.

I believe that this manuscript offers valuable insights into a pressing global issue and contributes to the discourse on conflict and humanitarian response. I have ensured that the manuscript adheres to rigorous standards of academic integrity, including the use of legitimate, valid, and reliable references.

Thank you for considering my manuscript.

I look forward to your feedback and am available for any further information or revisions that may be required.

Sincerely,

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Abstract

This article examines the October 2023 war on Gaza, focusing on its impact on healthcare systems. It starts with a historical overview of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict to contextualize the Gaza Strip's unique situation and the hostilities that began on October 7, 2023. The article then describes the war's notable feature: the deliberate targeting of the healthcare system. Finally, it explores the nature of the conflict through a necropolitical perspective.

Keywords: war, ethics, necro politics, human rights, Gaza

“The idea that some lives matter less is the root of all that is wrong with the world.”

— Paul Farmer [1]

Introduction

In recent months, the humanitarian crisis in Gaza has reached unprecedented levels of suffering and despair. The testimonies from those on the ground paint a stark picture of the dire conditions faced by civilians and medical professionals alike. As one healthcare worker lamented, “We have been trying to perform excruciatingly painful procedures, with no ketamine or even Tramadol. With nothing ...” (Abu Sitta, 2023). This highlights the severe shortages of essential medical supplies amid ongoing conflict.

The gravity of the situation is further underscored by another poignant account:

“The situation now is to die silently. Only death is all over around, no response, no help. Everything stays still” (Moghrabi, 2023). This statement reflects the pervasive sense of abandonment and helplessness that characterizes the current crisis in Gaza, where the bombardment and blockade have exacerbated the already dire humanitarian conditions.

These quotes set the stage for understanding the broader implications of the current crisis, emphasizing the severe impact on healthcare systems and the daily lives of individuals in Gaza. The situation is a culmination of long-standing conflict and recent escalations, illustrating the urgent need for international attention and intervention to address the humanitarian disaster unfolding in the region.

These statements may seem like a surreal, nightmarish depiction of a crumbling healthcare system, but they are real testimonies from surgeons treating the wounded in Gaza since October 7, 2023. By January 4, 2024, over 22,438 residents had been killed [2]. The first statement is from an X post by a Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF) surgeon at Al Ahli Hospital [3], while the second comes from a Gazan plastic and reconstructive surgeon [4] at Al Naser Hospital, who shared on his personal Facebook account the tragic experience of amputating a child's arm and leg before she ultimately succumbed to her injuries. The horror of such violence is magnified by the stark reality that, even amid devastation,

In Gaza, the concept of “order and limits” has been systematically violated by the ongoing Israeli invasion, which shows no signs of abating. Initial impressions of the narratives provided might suggest a mere breakdown of the healthcare system, but in reality, what is occurring is a deliberate and total destruction, violating international humanitarian law (IHL) which prohibits the targeting of medical facilities. Most of Gaza’s 36 hospitals are either completely non-functional or struggling to operate with severe shortages of essential supplies, while operating at 190% capacity [6].

The International Committee of the Red Cross president, Spoljaric, has remarked on the intolerable level of human suffering and the unacceptable lack of safe havens for civilians in Gaza, compounded by the military siege that hampers effective humanitarian responses [7]. Dr. Richard Peeperkorn, WHO representative in the occupied Palestinian territories, has described Gaza’s healthcare system as “crippled by the ongoing hostilities” [8].

This situation prompts a classic Machiavellian dilemma: do the ends justify the means? Is it permissible for political leaders to transgress deep moral boundaries in pursuit of what they consider a greater good for their own populations? To address this, it is essential to provide a brief historical overview of the conflict.

Brief Historical Background

The Israeli-Palestinian conflict has its roots in the early 20th century, beginning with the Balfour Declaration of November 2, 1917, when Britain promised to establish a Jewish homeland in Palestine [9]. This declaration disrupted the lives of Palestinians, as Jewish migration increased, especially during World War II when many Jews fled the Nazi regime. In 1947, a ship carrying Jewish refugees from Europe arrived in Palestine, then under British control. The ship’s sign, “The Germans destroyed our families and homes — Don’t you destroy our hopes,” highlighted the dire circumstances faced by Jewish refugees.

The Zionist movement, which promoted the idea of a Jewish homeland in Palestine, was based on the notion of “giving a land without people to a people without a land” [10]. This concept, akin to the colonial “Terra Nullius” ideology, disregarded the existing Palestinian population and sought to justify their displacement. Theodore Herzl, a key figure in Zionism, articulated this mindset by stating that new construction required the demolition of the old [11]. The ongoing settler colonialism has resulted in the continuous appropriation of Palestinian land [12].

The aftermath of the Holocaust and persistent antisemitism further fueled the Zionist claim to Palestine as a “promised land.” The State of Israel was proclaimed on May 14, 1948, celebrated by Israelis as Independence Day but remembered by Palestinians as Nakba (“the

Catastrophe”). Since then, Palestinians have faced ongoing displacement and oppression, with many living in the West Bank, Gaza, and neighboring Arab countries. The Gaza Strip, under blockade since 2007, is often described as the largest open-air prison in the world.

Britain’s promise of land it did not own marked the beginning of severe aggression against Palestinians, leading to the Israeli military occupation and numerous acts of resistance, often termed as the “Arab-Israeli Conflict.” Since 1987, Palestinians have achieved some notable “victories,” with international condemnation of Israeli human rights violations [12].

How the Current Invasion of Gaza is Different

On October 7, 2023, Hamas militants launched a major attack on Israel, marking one of the most intense assaults on the state in decades. The Middle East Monitor described this attack as a significant strategic and military blow, inflicting unprecedented casualties and capturing numerous Israelis [14]. The widespread coverage of the attack and subsequent Israeli Defense Forces’ actions on social media led to global awareness and condemnation. For the first time, many countries and populations (excluding their governments) began accusing Israel of genocide and ethnic cleansing, calling for a Free Palestine.

The War on Healthcare

The World Health Organization (WHO) set out its 2015-2030 agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), aiming to achieve universal health coverage and address health inequalities globally (SDG 3) [15]. Despite these efforts, healthcare systems in numerous conflict-ridden countries, such as Yemen, Iraq, Syria, Ukraine, South Sudan, and Palestine, continue to deteriorate, struggling with limited resources, shortages of trained personnel, and damaged facilities [16]. Historical analysis shows that wars severely impact healthcare infrastructure and escalate humanitarian crises, particularly affecting vulnerable populations. The responses from international medical and humanitarian organizations are often inadequate due to the compounded challenges of conflict and political instability.

The Geneva Convention and International Humanitarian Law (IHL) Rule 25 mandate that “military and civilian medical personnel exclusively assigned to medical duties must be respected and protected in all circumstances” [17]. Thus, attacks on healthcare workers and facilities are war crimes and clear breaches of IHL. The recent aggression in Gaza has intensified this issue, revealing a targeted assault on the healthcare sector—a war within a war [18]. The long-term consequences of such attacks will be severe, with lasting health problems and disease outbreaks anticipated as a result of the destruction of healthcare infrastructure.

The 2023 violence in Gaza is marked by an unprecedented level of aggression towards healthcare, including an infamous call from 45 influential Israeli rabbis to bomb hospitals [19] and an endorsement of this violence by 400 doctors [20]. Since October 7, at least 364 attacks on healthcare services have been recorded, with significant damage to facilities such as the Indonesian hospital in Gaza, which was bombed 35 times [18]. Healthcare workers have faced severe risks, including arrest and injury, exemplified by the arrest of the general director of Al-Shifa Hospital and his continued disappearance.

Dr. Mofokeng, the United Nations Special Rapporteur on the right to health, has declared that Gaza's health infrastructure is "completely destroyed," marking "the darkest time for the right to health in our lifetimes" [18]. Despite international laws and resolutions, efforts to halt the destruction of Gaza's healthcare system have been ineffective.

The deliberate dismantling of healthcare, along with the targeting of essential services like water, sewage, and food, will have enduring effects. The population is left without medical care, clean water, and adequate nutrition, leading to a rise in communicable diseases, respiratory illnesses, and other health issues. The only cancer hospital in Gaza was bombed twice in October [21], and the WHO has reported a dramatic increase in cases of diarrhea, especially among infants, and concerning levels of acute jaundice syndrome [22].

Further compounding the crisis are reports of the use of internationally banned weapons, including phosphorus and depleted uranium, which cause severe injuries and spread toxins [23]. The nature of the wounds—such as incendiary burns and guillotine-like amputations from fragmentation missiles—highlights the brutal effects of these weapons. The long-term health implications of such weaponry remain uncertain.

The war's impact extends beyond physical injuries, causing widespread malnutrition, displacement, and loss of essential medical records. These conditions contribute to a surge in mental health issues, including PTSD, depression, and trauma, particularly among children and healthcare workers. Save the Children reports that children are experiencing significant trauma symptoms, such as anxiety, nightmares, and emotional withdrawal [24]. The Executive Board of the WHO convened an emergency session to address the health crisis, while efforts are being made to increase medical aid and foreign healthcare workers' access to Gaza.

Despite the danger, healthcare workers in Gaza have continued to provide care until resources were utterly depleted, resorting to basic means like washing liquid and vinegar for wound treatment and performing surgeries without anesthesia. The tragic story of a surgeon losing his own son during an amputation, performed without anesthesia, highlights the extreme conditions faced by

healthcare providers [25]. Reports of triage decisions based on familial factors and the prevalence of severe fragmentation injuries emphasize the dire state of medical care [26].

Undercutting Healthcare as a Strategy of War

October 7, 2023, represents a Nietzschean moment where shared values and human rights principles, as outlined in documents like the Declaration of Human Rights and the Geneva Conventions, are not only devalued but outright rejected. These values are seen as “slave moralities” by those in power, who advocate for a will to power-based perspective on life and human rights. Nietzsche’s view that humans create their own values and judge what is injurious to themselves is evident in the current context [27].

Modern “überstates” (a term coined here to describe states with extreme control over their populations) operate under colonial settler ideologies that perpetuate a necropolitical framework. This framework devalues and dehumanizes the subjects under their control, dismissing their experiences and narratives through epistemic violence. Gazans, and Palestinians in general, have been subjected to over 75 years of dehumanization by the State of Israel. However, social media has begun to expose the brutal reality of their suffering, providing a platform for their voices and experiences.

As Paul Farmer noted, “human rights violations are not accidents; they are symptoms of deeper pathologies of power” [28]. The brutal tactics employed in Gaza reflect these deeper issues of power and control, revealing a disturbing disregard for human rights and a systemic approach to oppression.

Necro-politics and Healthcare

The assault on healthcare in Gaza exemplifies what Michel Foucault termed biopolitics—the mechanisms through which political strategies target the basic biological aspects of humanity, managing life and death. Foucault described this as the power to “make live and let die” and the emergence of a new right: the power to determine who lives and who dies [29]. In Gaza, this has transitioned from biopower, which focuses on individual lives, to necropower, which targets entire communities and regions.

Gaza represents a necropolitical paradigm similar to Giorgio Agamben's concept of the concentration camp, a space where the state of exception becomes the norm [30]. In this context, Gazans are reduced to a state of bare existence, fighting for survival while being deprived of basic rights and services. The West Bank camps are viewed as experimental zones for control and surveillance, where the state of exception is normalized [31]. The deliberate targeting of healthcare facilities, workers, and ambulances underscores this shift.

Dr. Hammam Aloh, a nephrologist at Al Shifa Hospital, exemplifies the tragic impact of this necropolitical environment. Despite the dangers, he chose to remain at his post, emphasizing the fundamental right to healthcare: “If I leave, who will treat my patients? We are not animals. We have a right to receive healthcare” [32]. This statement reflects a broader issue, highlighting how Palestinians have been dehumanized by some Israeli officials, reducing their lives to a state of inferiority [33].

Many healthcare workers in Gaza, like Dr. Hammam, demonstrate exceptional humanity and bravery, yet they are tragically lost rather than celebrated. This reality reflects a state that exerts control over an entire population by denying them essential services, challenging global definitions of values and rights. Gaza has become the extreme example of spatial exclusion, reminiscent of early forms of settler or genocidal colonialism [34].

Jewish philosopher Judith Butler, known for her work on the precariousness of life and the valuation of different lives, describes the situation in Gaza as a systematic undermining of basic livelihood, health, and well-being [35]. From a Butlerian perspective, Palestinians are dehumanized to such an extent that their deaths are not seen as worthy of grief. Butler argues that this treatment reflects a broader denial of humanity, suggesting that Palestinians are perceived as threats to a conceptual ideal of

humanity defended by Zionist politics and Western powers [35][36].

The tragic story of 11-year-old Anas, who requested water before dying after surgery, highlights the universal value of life. The surgeon’s final memory of Anas—providing him with water in his last moments—was shared widely, illustrating how precious life remains to many people despite attempts to devalue it [37].

Albert Camus’s Nobel Prize acceptance speech resonates strongly in this context: “Each generation doubtlessly feels called upon to reform the world. Mine knows that it will not reform it, but its task is perhaps even greater. It consists in preventing the world from destroying itself” [38]. This challenge underscores the profound responsibility we have to prevent further humanitarian crises and uphold the value of every life.

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